

SQLite Index Visualization: Structure

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Abstract: This article explores how SQLite stores and organizes index data on disk and in memory. It explains the structure of pages and cells inside a B-Tree, the main data structure used for indexes in SQLite. To better understand how indexes work, the author created custom C functions to extract and visualize index data, showing how pages and cells are linked and how data grows as records increase from 1 to 1,000,000. The article compares different index types - ascending, descending, expression-based, unique, partial, and multi-column - and shows how commands like VACUUM and REINDEX optimize storage. The visualizations help developers clearly see how index structures evolve and how SQLite efficiently manages data internally.

Keywords: SQLite, chart, index structure, B-Tree, data storage, visualization

After learning about indexes, I understood their basic structure, but I wanted to dig deeper — to explore the data structure, understand the algorithm, and learn how the index data is stored on disk. The theory and actual implementation can differ, so I decided to explore this topic further.

I wanted to see how a database management system (DBMS) stores an index in both disk and memory, and how it searches through an Index.

I chose SQLite for my experiments:

- it's a widely used DBMS, found in browsers, mobile apps, and operating systems;
- it's easier to debug: no separate server, just a client-side application;
- its codebase is smaller than MySQL or PostgreSQL but uses similar data structures for Indexes;
- it's open-source.

Node and Page Structure

According to SQLite [documentation](#), Indexes are stored in a B-Tree structure, which is a balanced tree where each node has multiple children.

It typically looks like this:

To understand how SQLite stores Nodes, let's look at the Page and Cell structures.

A Page (analog of a Node on SQLite) stores Cells data and has a link to its right child Page.

A Cell contains Index data, a rowId, and a link to its left child Page.

By default, each SQLite table row has a unique rowId, which works like a primary key if one isn't explicitly defined.

Here's a visual example of a B-Tree Index in SQLite:

Index data is stored on disk in this structure:

Page Header		Page Payload				
Right Child Number	Page Number	Cell Header	Cell Payload	...	Cell Header	Cell Payload
		Left Child Number	Data, RowID	...	Left Child Number	Data, RowID

Each Page has a fixed size, ranging from 512 to 65,536 bytes. Page and Cell headers use 4 bytes to store child links.

If we want to know child Page number - we need to read the header separately with this function:

```
get4byte(...)
```

For other Page and Cell data, we can use these C structures:

Page

sqlite/src/btreeInt.h

```

struct MemPage {
    Pgno pgno;           /* Page number for this page */
    u16 nCell;          /* Number of cells on this page, local and ovfl */
    u8 *aCellIdx;       /* The cell index area */
    u8 *aData;          /* Pointer to disk image of the page data */
    ...
};
  
```

Cell

sqlite/src/btreeInt.h

```
struct CellInfo {
    u8 *pPayload; /* Pointer to the start of payload */
    ...
};
```

To view index data, we can use [sqlite3 analyzer](#):

```
sqlite3_analyzer database.sqlite
...
Page size in bytes..... 4096
...
*** Index IDX of table TABLE_TEST
*****
Number of entries..... 1000
B-tree depth..... 2
Total pages used..... 4
..
```

This tool provides only general information about index.

Analyzing SQLite Source Code

After a few weeks of experimenting, I wrote my functions for index analysis.

You can view the code [here](#):

```
char *sqlite3DebugGetMemoryPayload(Mem *mem);

char **sqlite3DebugGetCellPayloadAndRowId(BtCursor *pCur, MemPage *pPage,
int cellIndex);

void sqlite3DebugBtreeIndexDump(BtCursor *pCur, int pageNumber);
```

The function reads the content of selected index and outputting data to STDOUT:

```
SQL query -> selected index -> stdout
```

Here's an example output:

```
sqlite3BtreeIndexDump: page, number=3, rightChildPageNumber=99
sqlite3BtreeIndexDump: cell, number=0, leftChildPageNumber=7, payload=384,
rowId=384
sqlite3BtreeIndexDump: cell, number=1, leftChildPageNumber=8, payload=742,
rowId=742
...
```

I packed everything into a docker if you want to test it:

```
docker run -it --rm -v "$PWD":/app/data --platform linux/x86_64
mrsuh/sqlite-index bash
```

You can use the script like this:

```
sh bin/dump-index.sh database.sqlite "SELECT * FROM table INDEXED BY index
WHERE column=1" dump.txt
```

dump.txt

```
sqlite3BtreeIndexDump: page, number=3, rightChildPageNumber=99
sqlite3BtreeIndexDump: cell, number=0, leftChildPageNumber=7, payload=384,
rowId=384
sqlite3BtreeIndexDump: cell, number=1, leftChildPageNumber=8, payload=742,
rowId=742
...
sqlite3BtreeIndexDump: page, number=99, rightChildPageNumber=-1
sqlite3BtreeIndexDump: cell, number=0, leftChildPageNumber=-1,
payload=9642, rowId=9642
sqlite3BtreeIndexDump: cell, number=1, leftChildPageNumber=-1,
payload=9643, rowId=9643
...
sqlite3BtreeIndexDump: page, number=7, rightChildPageNumber=-1
sqlite3BtreeIndexDump: cell, number=0, leftChildPageNumber=-1, payload=1,
rowId=1
sqlite3BtreeIndexDump: cell, number=1, leftChildPageNumber=-1, payload=2,
rowId=2
...
```

Great!

The next step was to display everything visually — an easy part of the process.

I found a library called [d3-org-tree](#) for visualizing index structures. Here's how it looked in the early stages:

However, there was a problem: I couldn't adjust the spacing between Pages, so as the tree became deeper and more Pages were added at each level, the image became too large and hard to read.

I tried adjusting it with JavaScript and CSS, but it didn't work well. After a few tries with [d3-org-tree](#), I decided that using text to display the structure would be simpler.

Example:

```
-----  
-----  
Total Pages: 29  
Total Cells: 1000  
-----  
-----  
Level: 1  
|=====|  
Pages: 1 |Page: 3 | RightChildPage: 53 |  
Cells: 27 |  
Cells: 29  
|=====|  
|Cell: 0 | LeftChildPage: 47 |  
RowId: 1 |  
|Payload:  
00000000000000000000000000000000 |  
-----|  
| * * * |  
-----|  
|Cell: 26 | LeftChildPage: 78 |  
RowId: 5 |  
|Payload:  
00000000000000000000000000000000 |  
|=====|  
-----  
-----  
Level: 2 |=====|  
|=====|  
Pages: 50 |Page: 3 | RightChildPage: 53 | Cells: 27 | |Page: 3 |  
RightChildPage: 53 | Cells: 27 |  
Cells: 400 |=====|  
|=====|  
|Cell: 0 | LeftChildPage: 47 | RowId: 1 | |Cell: 0 |  
LeftChildPage: 47 | RowId: 1 |  
|Payload: 00000000000000000000000000000000 | |Payload:  
00000000000000000000000000000000 |  
-----| |-----  
-----| |  
| * * * | |  
-----| |-----  
-----| |  
|Cell: 26 | LeftChildPage: 78 | RowId: 5 | |Cell: 26 |  
| LeftChildPage: 78 | RowId: 5 |  
|Payload: 00000000000000000000000000000000 | |Payload:  
00000000000000000000000000000000 |
```


Not bad, but I could go further.

PHP's [ImageMagick](#) extension lets us create images with more control over design and spacing than text alone. After about a dozen tries, here's the final version I came up with:

Index pages:2930
Index cells:1000000

The image now includes all the needed data and is easy to read.

In the top-left corner, there's general information about the Index.

Each level shows the total number of Pages and Cells.

Each Page shows its Page number, the link to its right child, and details about the first and last Cell.

Only a few Pages are shown per level, including the first and last Pages for each level.

The root Page is located at the first level.

Use this command to generate an image from the dump

```
php bin/console app:render-index --dumpIndexPath=dump.txt --
outputImagePath=image.webp
```

Now it's time to experiment!

We can create different data for the Indexes and explore what's inside them.

To start, it would be interesting to see how the Index size grows from 1 to 1,000,000 records.

Before each Index image, I'll show the table's data structure, the way the Index was made, and how the table was filled with data.

Index with 1 record

```
CREATE TABLE table_test (column1 INT NOT NULL);
INSERT INTO table_test (column1) VALUES (1);
CREATE INDEX idx ON table_test (column1 ASC);
```

Index pages:1
Index cells:1

Pages:1 Cells:1	
Page:3	Cells:1
RightChildPage:	
Cell:0	RowId:1
LeftChildPage:	
Payload:1	

One level, one Page, one Cell. Simple!

Index with 1000 records

```
CREATE TABLE table_test (column1 INT NOT NULL);
INSERT INTO table_test (column1) VALUES
(1),(2),(3),..., (998),(999),(1000);
CREATE INDEX idx ON table_test (column1 ASC);
```

Index pages:4
Index cells:1000

Pages:1 Cells:2			
Page:6		Cells:2	
RightChildPage:9			
Cell:0		RowId:435	
LeftChildPage:7		Payload:435	
Cell:1		RowId:843	
LeftChildPage:8		Payload:843	
Pages:3 Cells:998			
Page:7		Cells:434	
RightChildPage:		Page:9	
RightChildPage:		Cells:157	
Cell:0		RowId:1	
LeftChildPage:		Cell:0	
Payload:1		RowId:844	
Payload:844		LeftChildPage:	
		Payload:1000	
Cell:433		RowId:434	
LeftChildPage:		LeftChildPage:	
Payload:434		Payload:1000	

Index with 1.000.000 records

```
CREATE TABLE table_test (column1 INT NOT NULL);
INSERT INTO table_test (column1) VALUES
(1),(2),(3),..., (999998), (999999), (1000000);
CREATE INDEX idx ON table_test (column1 ASC);
```

Index pages:2930
Index cells:1000000

Now we've reached the image I used earlier as an example.

This Index has 3 levels, 2,930 Pages, and 1,000,000 Cells. The data was added in order, so for rowId = 1, column1 = 1.

Comparing ASC and DESC Indexes

Now, let's add two Indexes with different sort directions.

```
CREATE TABLE table_test (column1 INT NOT NULL);
INSERT INTO table_test (column1) VALUES
(1),(2),(3),..., (999998), (999999), (1000000);
CREATE INDEX idx_asc ON table_test (column1 ASC);
CREATE INDEX idx_desc ON table_test (column1 DESC);
```

Index pages:2930
Index cells:1000000

The ASC Index is the same as above, as ASC sorting is used by default.

The table's first entry, rowId=1,000,000, column1=1,000,000, payload=1,000,000, is in the last Cell of the rightmost Page.

The table's last entry, rowId=1, column1=1, payload=1, is in the first Cell of the leftmost Page.

Index with expression-based data

```
CREATE TABLE table_test (column1 TEXT NOT NULL);
INSERT INTO table_test (column1) VALUES
('{"timestamp":1}'), ('{"timestamp":2}'), ('{"timestamp":3}'), ..., ('{"timestamp":999998}'), ('{"timestamp":999999}'), ('{"timestamp":1000000}');
CREATE INDEX idx ON table_test (strftime('%Y-%m-%d %H:%M:%S',
json_extract(column1, '$.timestamp'), 'unixepoch') ASC);
```

Index pages:6851
Index cells:1000000

The Index now stores a string generated by the expression.
You can use more complex expressions, and the Index will save the only result.

Unique Index with NULL values

```
CREATE TABLE table_test (column1 INT)
INSERT INTO table_test (column1) VALUES
(1),(NULL),(NULL),...,(NULL),(NULL),(1000000);
CREATE UNIQUE INDEX idx ON table_test (column1 ASC);
```

Index pages:2198
Index cells:1000000

SQLite supports unique Indexes with NULL values.
This index looks like we are storing only non-NULL values.

After

Index pages:2930
Index cells:1000000

The tree must rebalance itself when new data is added. Creating an Index on existing data should be much more efficient.

Both Indexes look similar, but the second Index, with fewer Pages, should be faster.

	Total Pages	Total Cells
Before	3342	1000000
After	2930	1000000

VACUUM and REINDEX

To achieve similar optimization, we can rebuild an existing Index with these commands:

[VACUUM](#) recreates Indexes and tables with data:

```
CREATE TABLE table_test (column1 INT NOT NULL);
CREATE INDEX idx ON table_test (column1 ASC);
INSERT INTO table_test (column1) VALUES
(1),(2),(3),..., (999998), (999999), (1000000);
VACUUM;
```

	Total Pages	Total Cells
Before	3342	1000000
After	2930	1000000

[REINDEX](#) - recreates Indexes only:

```
CREATE TABLE table_test (column1 INT NOT NULL);
CREATE INDEX idx ON table_test (column1 ASC);
INSERT INTO table_test (column1) VALUES
(1),(2),(3),..., (999998), (999999), (1000000);
REINDEX idx;
```

	Total Pages	Total Cells
Before	3342	1000000
After	2930	1000000

After running VACUUM/REINDEX, the number of Pages in the Index decreased a lot.

Float-point Data in Indexes

```
CREATE TABLE table_test (column1 REAL NOT NULL);
INSERT INTO table_test (column1) VALUES
('1.14'),('2.14'),('3.14'),...,'999998.14'),('999999.14'),('1000000.14');
CREATE INDEX idx ON table_test (column1 ASC);
```

Index pages:4165
Index cells:1000000

Conclusion

Based on the work done, we saw how Indexes in SQLite are structured.

We looked at how record data is stored in memory and how the B-Tree organizes and accesses this data.

The visualization helped analyze and compare different Indexes.

To reproduce all of these examples, you can run the following:

```
docker run -it --rm -v "$PWD":/app/data --platform linux/x86_64
mrsuh/sqlite-index bash
sh bin/test-index.sh
```

Code and examples are available [here](#)

Next, I'll focus on visualizing Index-based searches and explore some interesting SQL queries.